

Title: Integrated Diagnostic Evaluation of a Radicular Cyst Using FNAC and CBCT: A Case Report and Literature Review.

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Abstract:

Radicular cysts are well described as inflammatory odontogenic cysts of endodontic origin that evolved from inflamed granulation tissue, circumscribed by a fibrous capsule in which the epithelial rests are stimulated by the inflammatory process, leading to the formation of an epithelium-lined cavity. Radicular cyst accounts for 50.25% of all odontogenic cysts and is the most frequent of all odontogenic cysts. The prevalence among the male gender is slightly higher (64.36%; M:F = 1.81) than the female gender. Radicular cyst occurs in all tooth-bearing areas of the jaws, although about 60% are found in the maxilla and 40% in the mandible. This case report highlights the significance of CBCT in aiding the diagnosis of the condition because of adequate spatial resolution and undistorted hard tissue information. Also highlights the significance of FNAC, which is a simple, safe, and minimally invasive investigation that can render a preoperative diagnosis of radicular cyst, in the light of clinic-radiological correlation.

Introduction:

Cystic lesions are defined as a pathologic cavity totally lined by the epithelium (true cyst) or partially lined by this tissue, maintaining contact with the injured tooth apex (pocket cyst)¹. Radicular cysts are well described as inflammatory odontogenic cysts of endodontic origin that evolved from inflamed granulation tissue, circumscribed by a fibrous capsule in which the epithelial rests are stimulated by the inflammatory process, leading to the formation of an epithelium-lined cavity².

Extensive carious lesions, defective restorations, iatrogenic orthodontic procedures, trauma, or parafunctional habits can precipitate an infectious or degenerative process in the root canals, which ultimately leads to a radicular cyst³.

Among odontogenic cysts, radicular cysts have been indicated to represent 54.6% in a literature review by Johnson et al⁴. Ramachandran Nair et al showed that out of 256 periapical lesions, a total of 39 (15%) were classified as radicular cysts after microscopic examination using serial sectioning⁵.

Several theories have been proposed for the origin of radicular cysts. One theory is nutritional deficiency; epithelial cells proliferate uncontrollably and die due to the inflammatory stimulus, generating a cystic cavity⁶. Another theory posits that an abscess in the connective tissue is surrounded by epithelial cells, forming a cyst⁷. A third theory involves epithelial proliferation, forming a three-dimensional structure that degenerates to create the cystic cavity⁶.

Ricucci et al. classify cystic lesions based on their communication with the root canals into pocket cysts (direct communication) and true cysts (no communication)⁷. Many radicular cysts are symptomless and are discovered when periapical radiographs are taken of teeth with nonvital pulps. Overall, however, radicular cysts are probably the most common cause of swelling of the jaws, and slowly enlarging swellings are often complained of. At first, the enlargement is bony hard, but as the cyst increases in size, the covering bone becomes very thin despite subperiosteal bone deposition, and the swelling then exhibits 'springiness' or 'eggshell crackling'. There may be buccal or palatal enlargement in the maxilla, whereas in the mandible it is usually labial or buccal and only rarely lingual. Only when the cyst has completely eroded the bone, the lesion will be fluctuant. Pain and infection are other clinical features of some radicular cysts⁸.

Radiographically, radicular cysts appear as radiolucent, rounded, or oval unilocular areas in the periapical region, often distinguished by a radio-opaque line associated with sclerotic bone. When the radiolucent area exceeds 1.6 cm and extends to the apices of neighboring teeth, an inflammatory radicular cyst is likely to occur⁹.

Differential diagnoses include periapical granuloma, bone scar, simple bone cyst, traumatic bone cyst, or keratinized odontogenic tumor. Diagnosis involves correlating clinical symptoms, pulp vitality tests, and radiographic findings, with histopathology providing definitive confirmation, in which fibrous connective tissue, granulation tissue, epithelium, and acute or chronic inflammatory cells are observed. Lymphocytes, plasmocytes, macrophages, and neutrophils predominate¹⁰.

This work aims to present a clinical case of an extensive radicular cyst, its clinical, radiographic, and histopathological characteristics, along with a review of the literature.

Case Presentation:

History Taking and Clinical Examination:

A 38-year-old male patient reported to the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology with the chief complaint of pain and swelling in the upper left front region of the jaw for 7 days. Pain was sudden in onset, mild, intermittent, and dull aching in nature. Pain was associated with swelling, which was initially small in size and gradually increased to attain its present size. Patient gives history of trauma 2-3 years back in the same region. On extraoral examination, no abnormality was detected [Figure 1].

On soft tissue examination, a single localized swelling was present over the anterior hard palate extending from mesial of 21 till distal of 22 along the mid palatal region. The size was approximately 2*2 cm in diameter. The shape was roughly oval. The surface was smooth. The colour was the same as that of the adjacent mucosa. On palpation, all the inspectory findings were confirmed. The consistency was soft. Tenderness was positive. Further, it was compressible and non-pulsatile [Figure 2].

On hard tissue examination, there was an Ellis class III fracture with 22. Tenderness was positive with 21 and 22. Also, generalized mild attrition was present. Based on the history and clinical examination, a provisional diagnosis of palatal abscess with 21, 22 and a differential diagnosis of radicular cyst and traumatic bone cyst with 21, 22 was given.

Further investigations, such as Intraoral Periapical Radiograph (IOPA), Orthopantomogram (OPG), Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT), Pulp Vitality Test (PVT), and Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC), were carried out.

Investigations:

IOPA [Figure 3], OPG [Figure 4], and CBCT [Figure 5]:

Location- A unilocular radiolucency was seen concerning the palatal aspect of 21, 22.

Extent- Extending from mesial of 11 to distal of 23.

Periphery- Well-defined

Shape- Roughly round

Internal Structure- Totally radiolucent

Size in Greatest Dimension- 13.30*9.45 mm [Figure 6].

Effects on Surrounding Structures- Loss of lamina dura with 21 and 22, and Loss of buccal cortical plate seen between 22 and 23, along with thinning of palatal cortical plate in the same region [Figure 7].

Pulp Vitality Test (PVT):

Performed with the Waldent Electric Pulp Tester.

21, 22, and 23 were non-vital; 11, 12, and 13 were vital.

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC):

Blood tinged straw coloured fluid was aspirated and sent for cytopathological evaluation [Figure 8].

Cytopathology:

Papanicolaou smear showed desquamated epithelial cells, necrotic debris, and cholesterol crystals suggestive of a Chronic Inflammatory Lesion [Figure 9].

Final Diagnosis:

Based on the above history, clinical examination, and various investigations, a final diagnosis of Infected Radicular Cyst with 21, 22, 23 was given.

Management:**Emergency Phase:**

Tablet Amoxyclav 625 mg (Amoxicillin 500 mg, Potassium Clavulanate 125 mg) B.D. for 3 days.

Tablet Zerodol SP (Aceclofenac 100 mg, Serratiopeptidase 15mg, Paracetamol 325 mg) B.D. for 3 days.

Tablet Pan 40 (Pantoprazole 40 mg) B.D. for 3 days.

Etiotropic Phase:

Oral prophylaxis.

Restorative Phase:

Root canal treatment with 21,22,23.

Surgical Phase:

Enucleation.

Maintenance Phase:

Advised to maintain oral hygiene.

Discussion:

Radicular cyst is also known as root end cyst, periapical cyst, and cystic apical periodontitis. Radicular cyst occurs in all tooth-bearing areas of the jaws, although about 60% are found in the maxilla and 40% in the mandible. The anterior region of the maxilla and premolar region of the mandible are more frequently involved than other parts of the jaw bone. There are several possible reasons for this. In addition to the hazard posed by dental caries, maxillary incisors in the past had more frequently silicate restorations placed in them, with consequent high risk to their pulps. Second, there is the high prevalence of palatal invaginations in the maxillary lateral

incisors and the frequency with which pulp death supervenes in these teeth. Third, maxillary anterior teeth are probably more prone than others to traumatic injuries, which may lead to pulp death¹¹.

Nair classified radicular cysts into bay cysts and true cysts. In bay cysts, there are open bags where the cyst lumen is continuous with the necrotic root canal. In true cysts, there are structurally independent lesions inside the body of the periapical lesion (apical periodontitis) without continuity with the root canal¹².

Radicular cysts usually present as an osteolytic lesion at the periapical area of a tooth with an infected necrotic pulp on conventional radiography and cone beam computed tomography. It is believed that if an osteolytic periapical lesion is more than 2 cm² in diameter, it may be a cystic lesion¹³. In addition, if a well-demarcated periapical osteolytic lesion is bordered by a thin rim of cortical bone, there is a strong probability that the lesion is a cyst. Radicular cysts are mostly asymptomatic unless they become infected¹⁴.

In the Initial Stage of pathogenesis, bacterial endotoxins cause inflammation in the apical region of a nonvital tooth, which leads to the proliferation of epithelial cells of Malassez.

In the Cyst Development Stage of pathogenesis, proliferative epithelial cells serve as building blocks for cyst wall development. This occurs due to the simultaneous decomposition of epithelial and granulation tissue and convergence of multiple cavities, with subsequent epithelialization.

In the Cyst Growth Stage of pathogenesis, due to the decomposition of epithelial cells, leukocytes, and the accumulation of plasma exudates, the osmolality of the cyst fluid becomes higher than that of the serum. As a result, hydrostatic internal pressure becomes greater than capillary pressure. Tissue fluid therefore diffuses into the cyst, making it increase in size. With osteoclastic bone resorption, the cyst expands. Other bone-resorbing factors, such as prostaglandins, interleukins, and proteinases, from inflammatory cells and cells in the peripheral portion of the lesion, permit additional cyst enlargement¹⁵.

The management of radicular cyst involves the extraction of the involved teeth, or endodontic therapy, and careful curettage of the periapical tissue. The cyst does not recur if the surgical removal is thorough. In case of a primary tooth, marsupialization is considered rather than enucleation to save the permanent tooth bud. Eruption of the permanent tooth is then monitored. If the cystic sac is badly fragmented, leaving epithelial remnants, or if a periapical

granuloma is incompletely removed with epithelial rests remaining, a residual cyst may develop in this area months or even years later. If untreated, the radicular cyst slowly increases in size at the expense of the surrounding bone¹⁶.

Conclusion:

Radicular cyst is an everyday disorder unearthed in the oral cavity, which is asymptomatic when small and diagnosed incidentally on radiographic examination. The current concept in the management of radicular cysts is to use nonsurgical means. However, depending on the size and extent of the lesion, surgical management might be necessary for achieving success. Radiographic examination is important prior to the removal of teeth. Moreover, coarse radicular cysts can lead to a major rate of morbidity. This case report highlights the significance of CBCT in aiding the diagnosis of the condition because of adequate spatial resolution and undistorted hard tissue information. Also highlights the significance of FNAC, which is a simple, safe, and minimally invasive investigation that can render a preoperative diagnosis of radicular cyst, in the light of clinic-radiological correlation.

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Figure 1: Extraoral profile of patient

Figure 2: Palatal swelling w.r.t. 21 and 22

Figure 3: IOPA w.r.t 21 and 22

Figure 4: OPG

Figure 5: CBCT 3D view

Figure 6: CBCT cross-sectional view

Figure 7: CBCT axial view

Figure 8: Sample for FNAC. Blood tinged straw coloured fluid was aspirated.

Figure 9: Cytopathology report.